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Food industry communication with next generation consumers: knowledge, engagement, empowerment, food values

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<i>Titill</i>	Food industry communication with next generation consumers: knowledge, engagement, empowerment, food values		
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<p>Ágrip á íslensku:</p>	<p>Fólk færir sífellt fjær frumframleiðslu matvæla og tenging við hráefni og vinnslu þess er oft óljós. Ungt fólk er neytendur framtíðarinnar. Viðhorf þeirra og traust til matvæla skiptir matvælaframleiðendur því miklu máli. Þarfir og gildi ungs fólks eru ekki endilega þau sömu og eldra fólks. Markmið verkefnisins WeValueFood var að leita leiða til að auka skilning og þekkingu ungs fólks þannig að það átti sig á gildum og verðmætum matvæla og verði meðvitaðri um mat í víðu samhengi.</p> <p>Þrjár vinnustofur voru haldnar á vegum Matís, þar sem nemendur á háskólastigi og íslenskur matvælaframtíðarinnar voru leiddir saman. Vinnustofurnar beindust að núverandi samskiptamynstri og upplýsingagjöf iðnaðarins til neytenda og var markmiðið að styðja við samskipti matvælaframtíðarinnar við neytendur framtíðarinnar. Ýmis matvælafyrirtæki og hagsmunaaðilar komu að vinnustofunum og unnu með ungum neytendum við að skilgreina matvælagildi og eiga samtál um samskiptaleiðir. Áhersla var lögð á að auka áhuga og þekkingu á matvælum til að stuðla að því að næstu kynslóðir taki skynsamlegar og upplýstar ákvarðanir í fæðuvali sínu. Vinnustofurnar þrjár fóru fram á netinu haustið 2020: 1) Með nemendum á háskólastigi – til að kanna matargildi þeirra og álit á núverandi samskiptaleiðum matvælaframtíðarinnar, 2) Með þátttakendum úr matvælaframtíðarinnar – til að kanna hvernig þeir upplifa næstu kynslóð neytenda og hvernig matvælaframtíðarinnar getur stutt við menntun/þekkingu og þátttöku í matartengdum málefnum og 3) Með nemendum á háskólastigi og þátttakendum úr matvælaframtíðarinnar – til að kynna hugmyndir matvælaframtíðarinnar og samskiptaleiðir, og kanna viðbrögð nemenda.</p> <p>Nemendur lögðu mikla áherslu á umhverfisáhrif, þar sem gegnsæi og heiðarleiki eru lykilatriði fyrir jákvæða ímynd og traust til matvælaframtíðarinnar. Ungt fólk vill vita meira um það hvernig matur er framleiddur og ekki síður hvað felst í framleiðsluferlinu. Þau vildu sjá meira um hvernig matvæli á Íslandi eru framleidd, hvort heldur sem er á samfélagsmiðlum, heimasíðum matvælafyrirtækja eða með merkingum matvæla. Það sem ungt fólk kallaði eftir voru meðal annars staðfestar upplýsingar um allt frá uppruna til matreiðslu og geymsluleiðbeininga. Áhersla var lögð á að upplýsingarnar þyrftu að vera staðfestar af hlutlausum aðilum eins og vísindafólki. Þátttakendur úr matvælaframtíðarinnar voru almennt meðvitaðir um þarfir ungs fólks hvað varðar upplýsingar og samskiptaleiðir, en voru oft í erfiðleikum með að mæta þessum þörfum m.a. vegna kostnaðar og tíma. Matvælaframtíðarinnar kallaði eftir samstarfi við yfirvöld til að koma á móts við þarfir ungs fólks varðandi þekkingu og menntun til að tryggja að fullnægjandi og vísindalega sannreyndar upplýsingar verði aðgengilegar öllum. Ein þeirra lausna sem lögð var til af hálfu iðnaðarþátttakenda gæti hæglega svarað þörfum ungs fólks fyrir sértæka matvælaþekkingu, sem gæti á sama tíma stuðlað að auknum áhuga og þátttöku ungs fólks. Þessi lausn snéri að matarvísindavef, sem stýrt yrði af óháðum aðilum, svo sem háskólum, til að miðla vísindalega sannreyndum upplýsingum án hagsmunaárekstra. Með vinnustofunum skapaðist áhugavert samtál milli nemenda og matvælaframtíðarinnar, sem gaf mikilvæga innsýn bæði fyrir neytendur og matvælaframtíðarinnar. Mikilvægt er að fylgja vinnustofunum eftir og styrkja samtál og upplýsingaflæði milli neytenda og framtíðarinnar til að mæta þörfum neytenda framtíðarinnar.</p> <p>WeValueFood var styrkt af Evrópusambandinu í gegnum EIT Food. Auk Matís og Háskóla Íslands, komu Universidad Autónoma de Madrid og IMDEA Food Institute á Spáni, EUFIC í Belgíu, Koppert í Hollandi, University of Cambridge og University of Reading í Bretlandi, University of Helsinki í Finnlandi, University of Turin á Ítalíu, University of Warsaw í Póllandi og Flatev í Sviss að verkefninu. Verkefninu var í heild stýrt af Institute for Global Food Security, Queen's University Belfast, Norður Írlandi.</p>
<p>Lykilorð á íslensku:</p>	<p><i>Matvælaframtíðarinnar, Neytendur, Fræðsla, Lýðheilsa, Nýsköpun</i></p>

<p><i>Summary in English:</i></p>	<p>Food consumption trends have increased the gap between primary food production. The proximity to production of raw materials and food processing has become more unclear to many consumers. Young people are the consumers of the future. Their attitude towards food is therefore important to food producers. Their needs and values are not necessarily the same as those of older consumers. The aim of the WeValueFood project was to find ways to increase the understanding and strengthen young people's knowledge and understanding so that they better appreciate the values of food and become more aware of food in a wider context.</p> <p>Three online workshops on food values of next generation consumers (NGCs) were carried out in Iceland in the autumn of 2020, by Matis in collaboration with the University of Iceland. The communication between university students of diverse study categories and food industry was explored within the three workshops: 1) With students - to assess their food values and opinions on the current food industry communication; 2) With industry participants – to understand how they perceive the NGCs and how they can help to educate and engage them with food; 3) With students and industry – to present industry’s ideas of communication and receive students feedback on industries communication strategies.</p> <p>The students emphasised environmental impact of foods, transparency, and honesty in communication for a positive image of and trust in food producers. They wanted to know more about how food is made, either on social media or food industry websites, or with food labels. Emphasis was placed on information about everything from origin and environmental labels to cooking and storage guidelines. Not less important, the information needed to be verified by a responsible independent third party, such as scientists. The food industry participants were generally aware of NGC's information needs and communication channels, but struggled to meet these needs, mainly due to cost and time. The food industry needed cooperation with authorities to educate the next generation on food related issues, to fulfil the NGC needs for knowledge, with scientifically valid and trustworthy information available for everyone. One of the idea pitches from the industry summarised the overall need for knowledge and communication, both for food industry and NGC that could improve food involvement and engagement. The pitch was about food science website, supervised by independent parties, such as universities, to provide fact based, scientifically correct information, without any conflicts of interest.</p> <p>WeValueFood, was supported by EU through EIT Food, was a two-year collaborative project between Matis, University of Iceland, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid (UAM-IMDEA) and IMDEA Food Institute in Spain, EUFIC í Belgium, Koppert in the Netherlands, University of Cambridge and University of Reading in England, University of Helsinki in Finland University of Turin in Italy, University of Warsaw in Poland and Flatev in Switzerland. The whole project was managed by Institute for Global Food Security, Queen's University Belfast, North Ireland.</p>
<p><i>English keywords:</i></p>	<p><i>Food industry, Consumers, Education, Public health, Innovation</i></p>

Table of contents

1. Introduction	1
2. Methodology	1
2.1 Workshop participants.....	1
2.2 Workshop procedure	2
2.3 Data analysis	4
3. Results.....	5
3.1 Workshop with students.....	5
3.2 Workshop with industry	6
3.3 Workshop with students and industry.....	9
3.4 Evaluation of workshops.....	12
4. Conclusions and recommendations.....	12
Acknowledgements	13
References	14

1. Introduction

The ultimate aim of The WeValueFood project was to impact society in ways that will educate, engage and advance the next generations knowledge, understanding and appreciation of food generally (nutrition, health, sustainability, security etc.). In 2020, the focus in WeValueFood was on piloting and testing different approaches to enhance food engagement among society, specifically, next generation consumers.

A part of this work, concentrated on helping industry learn/re-learn how to communicate with next generation audiences, outside of the typical marketing streams of communication. The focus was placed on industry's current engagement and communication patterns with consumers to investigate how best they could communicate with future consumers about food. The objective was to help industry (for example, producers, processors and retailers) re-learn how they could communicate with consumers in a constructive, positive and healthy way.

Industry partners from four pilot countries were invited to work with consumers and participate in workshops using student/industry communication, similar to reversed 'Dragon's Den' type scenarios. In each country, three types of workshops were carried out: 1) with students within the age of 18-26 years; 2) with industry; and 3) combined workshop where the industry participants pitched their new means of communication to the students. This third workshops with students and industry were used to evaluate industry ideas. Student workshops were completed to explore how students perceive industry's current food related messages. Results from the student workshops were provided as stimuli at the industry workshops to generate conversation on new mechanisms/means of communicating/engaging with young consumers. The industry partner's level of involvement and the process of engagement was documented and evaluated for efficacy and outcomes used to determine the usefulness of this type of co-creation.

The overall results of the workshop series in the four pilot countries are described in Sveinsdóttir et al (2020). The work described in this report are the results of the workshops carried out in Iceland, by Matis in collaboration with the University of Iceland. Matis chose to explore the relationship between university level students of diverse study categories and food industry within food processing, retail, wholesale and agricultural producer's organisation.

2. Methodology

2.1 Workshop participants

Students

The students were recruited in August to September 2020 via direct or snowball method within Matis and the University of Iceland community. For this purpose, emails were sent to potential recruiters or student participants including inclusion criteria and brief information about the project and workshops aims. Student inclusion criteria were as follows:

- ✓ University student (different educational fields)
- ✓ 18-26 years
- ✓ Interest in food related topics
- ✓ Availability and willingness to take part in the online workshops (1 and 3)

For students participating, vouchers of 5000 ISK were offered.

Workshop 1 was held in three parts, workshop 1.1; 1.2 and-1.3. Ten students, six females and four males undertaking different studies took part. Their studies included agricultural science, architecture, creative sustainability and food technology, food science, geography, health science, nature and environmental sciences, social science, and sports. They were all in the age range 18-26 years.

Food industry

Food industry participants were first contacted in May and June 2020 by email, followed by a phone call. The email to industry participants included information about the projects and workshops aims. Industry participants inclusion criteria was as follows:

- ✓ Occupation within food industry (different food industry fields)
- ✓ Representative from primary production, processing or retail
- ✓ Connection to food/food products in domestic market
- ✓ Individuals involved in communication/marketing or food product development
- ✓ Availability and willingness to take in the online workshops (2 and 3)

Before the workshops, the participants received information sheet about the background, aim and procedure of the workshops, and informed consent form to sign electronically via Taktikal (<https://taktikal.is/>). Each participant signed the form using their electronic ID via their smart phones, as well as the responsible person at Matis.

In workshop 2, five industry representatives took part, from different parts of the food value chain. However, they all worked within marketing and communication. In workshop 3, seven of the students from workshop 1.1-1.3 took part, five females and two males, but all industry representatives from workshop 2 took part.

2.2 Workshop procedure

Timing of the workshops was aimed at hours most convenient for participants, namely after school hours for students, and close to end of workday for industry participants. The mutual student/industry workshop timing aimed at meeting both groups half-way (Table 1).

Table 1. Workshop schedule (online, Teams)

Workshop no.	Workshop theme	Date and time
1.1	Students (n = 3)	14.09.2020 at 19.30-21.30
1.2	Students (n = 3)	15.09.2020 at 19.30-21.30
1.3	Students (n = 4)	16.09.2020 at 19.30-21.30
2	Industry (n = 5)	22.09.2020 at 14.00-16.00
3	Students (n = 7) and industry (n = 5)	28.09.2020 at 15.00-17.00

Due to covid-19 restrictions online workshops on Teams were conducted, instead of face-to-face workshops. In order to secure a smooth process in students' workshop, it was decided to run three separate workshops with students (Workshop no 1.1, 1.2 and 1.3 – see table 1).

In each workshop, main facilitator led the workshop and two secretaries took notes. The workshops were recorded for analysis purposes.

Workshop guidelines and discussion frame were designed in collaboration of researchers within the WeValueFood project and were used in the same manner in all workshops.

2.2.1 Workshop with students

Introduction section was set to 30 minutes. At the beginning of the workshop, slides were presented describing the workshop agenda, aims and previous results during WeValueFood work in 2019, to shed light on next generation needs regarding increased food engagement, knowledge and needs as well as food industry's views on engaging with next generation consumers.

Group work session was set to 80 minutes and covered 1) discussions on current communication with next generation consumers, food values and how participants preferred industry to communicate with next generation consumers outside of the typical marketing streams of communication and 2) students discussions and suggestions on optimal strategy for industry communication outside of the typical marketing streams of communication.

Sum-up session was set to 10 minutes and included a summary of the workshop discussions, presented by the facilitator. The facilitator introduced shortly the aim of the industry workshop (workshop 2), and the aim and procedure of the joint student and industry workshops with industry (workshop 3). All students were invited to take part in workshop 3.

2.2.2 Workshop with industry

Introduction section (30 minutes). At the beginning of the workshop, slides were presented describing the workshop agenda, aims and previous results during WeValueFood work in 2019, to shed light on next generation needs regarding increased food engagement, knowledge and needs as well as food industry's views on engaging with next generation consumers.

Group work session (80 minutes) covered 1) discussions on how the industry representatives felt about their current communication with next generation consumers, their companies food values and if they were currently communicating with next generation consumers outside of the typical marketing streams of communication and how they thought food industry should communicate with next generation consumers outside of the typical marketing streams of communication and 2) Industry discussions and suggestions on optimal strategy for industry communication outside of the typical marketing streams of communication. ***Before part 2 in the group work session took place***, the main results from Workshops 1.1-1.3 were presented to industry participant.

Sum-up session (10 minutes) included a summary of the workshop discussions, presented by the facilitator. The facilitator introduced shortly the aim and procedure of the joint student and industry workshops with industry (workshop 3). All industry representatives in Workshop 2 were invited to take part in workshop 3 and pitch their communication ideas to next generation consumer (students). For preparation, the industry representatives were explained what to consider during preparation of their pitches (also sent by email after the workshop):

"Here we are looking for ideas from you/your company, ideas for a strategy for new means of communication with emphasis on communication that could help increase knowledge, engagement

and interest in food related topics in general. Within this frame, both communication with and dissemination to next generation consumers can be embedded. You can also present e.g.:

- *which information about the product or the production process to you think could be relevant to next generation consumer*
- *handling, storage, use of food leftovers*
- *your emphasis regarding food values*
- *limitations regarding communication to next generation consumers, e.g. as discussed during Workshop 2 about company visits, materials or school visits” (translated from Icelandic)”*
-

2.2.3 Workshop with students and industry

This introduction section (30 minutes). At the beginning of the workshop, slides were presented describing the workshop agenda, aims and summarised results from Workshop 1.1-1.3 and Workshop 2. Emphasis was placed on detecting gaps or discrepancy in views and needs of next generation consumers and industry representatives.

Industry pitches (90 minutes) were presented by the industry representatives, one by one, in total five pitches, each lasting 5-10 minutes. After each pitch, the students were given the opportunity to ask questions and provide feedback. Further discussions were facilitated revisiting topics such as embedding trust, food values and interest.

Sum-up session and near future outlook (20 minutes) included a summary of the workshop discussions, presented by the facilitator. The facilitator also summarised findings across the workshops and asked for feedback from participants on how effective they believed this process has been in determining new strategies for communication and if such workshops could be used as a means of solving key challenges in the future. As the workshop time frame had expanded, students were asked to send via email a list of up to 5 DOs and 5 DONTs for food industry to follow in communication to the main facilitator.

2.3 Data analysis

The workshops were conducted and recorded using Microsoft Teams. Transcriptions were made from all the recordings from the workshops and the transcripts were used for further analysis. The transcripts included the Group-work sessions and the Sum-up sessions from workshops with the students and the workshop with the industry and the Industry pitches and the Sum-up sessions from the workshop with students and industry together.

Thematic analysis was used to analyse the transcripts from the workshops. Themes and patterns were identified and listed in a codebook from each workshop. Number of comments from each participant (students and industry) were listed in each suitable theme section. Besides, quotes were made from each participant that reflected their comments in each suitable theme section.

3. Results

3.1 Workshop with students

It was clear that **students did not feel the Icelandic food industry was communicating to their generation**, in that they found it close to invisible, or that the communication was monotonous. This lack of information from the industry and food producers may be seen as big gap between them and consumers.

“I have never noticed anything from the food industry” (Male, student)

The students considered food industry invisible on social media, but would like to see increased communication through that channel, either by using social media influencers or be visible themselves. However, many of the students **don’t trust influencers on social media** and it is important for the industry to be aware of the **critical thinking of this generation**. However, the students were generally positive towards the Icelandic industry.

“This [our generation] is a really critically thinking generation” (Female, student)

The main food values were **environmental impact** of the food production and that of the final product itself, and the students wanted to see the **carbon footprint on more Icelandic products**, as well as the **origin of the products**. **Nutrition** value was important to the students and most of them choose products with the **fewest and most natural ingredients**.

“Young people are well aware of the environmental impact of their consumption” (Male, student)

Students want the industry to emphasize and **minimize the processing** of products, add as **few ingredients** as they can to the product.

While some students did not think food industry representatives should visit schools due to potential conflicts of interest, other students thought **food industry should be visiting schools** and educating the students about healthy food. Food industry should invite students and all consumers for a **tour around their production**, or the industry could make **videos of their production and post them online** as not all food producers can invite guests to their production. This approach would be good for the industry because they can educate consumers about the origin of their products and why they use certain methods and ingredients in their production. This information could also be visible on **their website or their Instagram page**. In all materials presented by industry, it is important to remember that **honesty is the key to generating trust**. It might also be feasible if **independent individuals/stakeholders** could educate consumers, as some students don’t trust the industry to educate people that are supposed to be buying their product.

“I only trust them if they are honest” (Female, student)

“Easy for consumers to verify the information from producers because there is so much information available” (Female, student)

To generate interest from the next generation consumers, the industry could partner up with **influencers** and invite them to their production or visit stores and introduce their products. However, all the **information must be short and interesting**, young consumers do not watch long videos on social media, they need to get quick and interesting information. **Main opportunities are within sustainability and environmental impact** and food producers that discuss and advertise their ways to

decrease the environmental impact by for example decreasing their plastic use in the production could generate much interest and trust from this age group. One of the biggest **challenges is the critical thinking** in this age group and the vast amount of information available online, as well as the demand for entertainment and quick information.

The students ideas for the optimal strategy for industry communication outside of the typical marketing streams of communication, was for the **food producers to be visible in local stores and have accessible recipes and all the ingredients for that recipe available** close by. This could be important as many young consumers don't really know how to cook properly. As this generation is focused on sustainability and environmental issues, it would be helpful if the producers **could make videos of how to cook from their products** and provide information on **how to store** their product and **ideas to cook from leftovers**. The number of products for specific groups like vegans, should be increased, and labelling towards such groups should be visible. All of this could be available with **QR quotes**. To decrease food waste, it could also be wise to offer smaller doses, for people living alone, to decrease food waste.

“QR quotes with videos of how you make a meal from this ingredient, the food production, recipes and more” (Female, student)

To increase the food industry visibility, they should **contribute to the society**, e.g. environmental issues. Also, in general, there must be more communication between the industry and the consumers, both ways, welcoming suggestions from young consumers and respond to their requests. For this, **social media** would be the optimal communication channel to communicate to the next generation consumers either by using influencers or be visible themselves, with focus on interesting and short messages to grab the attention of young consumers. To capture attention, and shed light on their values, the food industry could use **games on their website** such as a quiz.

“Contribute to the society like planting trees to even out their carbon footprint” (Male, student)

“There should be a system for consumers to comment on what they want to change and improve” (Female, student)

“Food producers should have social media accounts and use short messages” (Female, student)

“Games and questionnaires about the products and the production on food producer’s website and the winner gets some of their product” (Male, student)

3.2 Workshop with industry

The food industry participants generally considered **the current level of communication with consumers** and NGCs as good (although NGCs themselves found it close to non-existing). NGCs contact companies as they seek more information about nutritional values, cooking methods, and appropriate treatments for various foods. Companies try to answer the most frequent questions by sending out messages, but it is difficult to find the right place for the information to appear depending on for who it is intended.

“I experience the communication as a curiosity from the consumer.” (Female, Industry)

“Schools communicate a lot with us about projects or education for the students.” (Female, Industry)

One of the main challenges are the new means of communication, **not the least to young consumers. NGCs ask a lot of questions, but demand or expect quick answers, require high standard information material and they also generally have positive attitudes.** The food industry participants feel that the **next generation consumers may lack knowledge** about how food is made, processed, or even cooked. Food industry companies are hesitant to reach out to schools or young people because it could look like a propaganda or advertisement rather than educational material. Instead, they try to approach young consumers differently, e.g. by being positive and willing to collaborate if schools reach out to them and to present their work within innovation, with emphasis on opportunities such work may have, to strike up a conversation with consumers.

Companies are not allowed to visit schools, but it may be an opportunity that schools are allowed to visit companies. **Current communication channels** are mainly via visits from schools to companies, emails and farmers markets, and social media communication.

“Young consumers ask a lot of questions through social media.” (Female, industry)

“Consumers communicate with us through email when they are looking for information about something.” (Female, industry)

What consumers want to know about food are mostly two things. Number one is **responsibility** of the company in the food chain like, is the company aware of the origin or production method of the food material they are using, why they are using it and how it affects their social responsibility.

“They [next generation consumers] want to know about packaging and responsibility in the production.” (Female, Industry)

The second is **transparency** of the journey from raw material to plate.

“where the product comes from.” (Female, industry)

“The origin.” (Female, Industry)

The food industry participants try to respond to request from consumers to their best ability, as responses to requests via social media, emails and during visits from schools.

The food industry participants seemed already have adapted to new **communication methods**, towards NGCs. **The main barrier** is that there is not just one channel where everyone can be reached. With growing media streaming service and technology, the algorithm targets depending on one’s interests, making it more difficult to reach those that don’t want to listen. Also, false news is easily spread, not the least by popular social media influencers. Other barriers were related to **lack of knowledge, lack of critical thinking and lack of time.** **The main opportunities** were seen in making food production interesting in terms of innovation and creativity, meeting new demands, and evoking interest via documentaries and TV shows.

“Many [young people] don't know how to cook and must get precise instructions.” (Female, industry)

“Visit schools and talk about innovation and inspire them to be creative.” (Female, industry)

“Documentaries and TV shows – Children are very interested in cooking shows for example” (Female, industry)

How industry should provide information about the products and production was mainly seen as providing information via the food industries **own websites**. Although not all industry participants considered it their responsibility to educate NGCs, they should be the ones that educate consumers about their own company products. **Food values** as nutrition value need to be emphasised, and in line with NGCs interest, the **carbon footprint**, and the **necessity of using specific ingredients and plastic in food packaging** needs to be communicated to NGCs. **The industry participants see a need for a common platform**, where food producers could use to explain food production.

“Available information on food producer’s website.” (Female, industry)

“It’s our responsibility to educate about what consumers can do with our products.” (Female, Industry)

“Children don’t know the basics, like nutrition value.” (Female, Industry)

“We want to be able to use the carbon footprint.” (Female, Industry)

“People should be able to communicate to producers and for example ask why do you use plastic here? (Female, Industry)

“Need a good platform to explain our decisions about plastic and why we do things the way we do.” (Female, industry)

Trust is an important, long-term project and **transparency** is essential in this context, especially among NGG.

“You don’t get trust over one night it’s a long-term project. The more transparency the more trust.” (Female, industry)

“Increase trust by providing new educational material in schools.” (Female, industry)

“Educate children about regulations and surveillance so they understand we have to obey rules.” (Female, industry)

Toward optimal strategy, it was emphasised by the industry participants that there is a **lack of understanding and education** on nutritional values and how or why some foods are processed. **To build trust, the lack of knowledge needs to be overcome.**

Food processing is perceived as negative by too many consumers and mainly done to make more profit. Although food processing may increase yield, utilisation and shelf life we are in the end wasting less food and ensuring food safety. When consumers lack this kind of information, it is not surprising that people have lack of trust towards the food industry. To build up trust the **main key is general food related knowledge**.

Labelling products with carbon footprint is desired, but it is expensive and time consuming. The industry participants would like to see an organization or association that would provide information on food related matters in understandable, simple, but at the same time, done in a professional way.

Barriers: Lack of knowledge (nutrition, cooking skills, regulations and production), lack of critical thinking, demand for fast solutions and responses, lack of trust towards industry, negative attitude towards plastic and palm oil among NGC and false information (e.g. via social influencers). The industry doesn’t have the resources, time and budget for carbon footprints calculations. There is a lack of mutual platform for the industry.

Opportunities: Evoke interest via documentaries or TV shows, smaller proportion packaging, food is for everyone and everyone must eat, platform to deliver knowledge and explain why things are done a certain way. Create interest and curiosity about food.

"In order to reach NGCs attention, the health authorities need to focus on not short campaigns, but also on interesting short footages/videos that are distributed to these media, about information from seed to product in different sectors and where to reach it" (Female, industry).

3.3 Workshop with students and industry

There is clearly a gap between food industry and NGCs. The NGCs require fast responses, and lack information on food and food-related issues. Information that is easily accessible and in simple language, but often information that is difficult for the industry to provide, such as carbon footprint.

With the increased availability of solid information on food and food production/processing, it can be expected that trust in the food industry will increase as suspicion decreases as people become better informed. Eating and consuming food is one of our basic needs. Everyone needs to eat, and everyone thinks about food, so this issue concerns everyone.

The pitches by industry were generally well perceived, by students but their main concerns were they often wanted more details on the production, which was generally not covered.

Pitch 1: "How it's made". Currently the company has information on the company's web page about product usage and utilization, project partnership with chef students and photographs used in marketing. The pitch was on short "how it's made" videos about food production "from farm to fork" that could be shared through social media or as educational material in high schools.

The students felt more details should be included. There should be a good balance of education and marketing.

Pitch 2: Food Science web page (matarvisindavefurinn.is). This would be a source reviewed by independent professionals, e.g. within the university community, based on Q/A. Companies could raise funds for the project by purchasing space for videos promoting their production and its benefits, fact-checked by the site's editors. This web page would also have recipe banks with videos where you are taught to cook step by step and everyone can upload videos, both companies and bloggers. The web page would host a podcast with fun food enthusiasts, on hot topics. Companies and independent experts are even invited to come together and have a discussion, supervised by the podcast host.

The students felt It was important that the source behind the information is objective and non-beneficial in order to earn trust of the general public, but there was a high need for a reliable source like this and had the most positive attitudes towards the idea.

Pitch 3: "five different ways". **1.The school – Workshops:** Workshops by companies, like "from a farm to fork" or a "day of food" at school where you get participants to take the potato or milk or pick up different elements according to school levels. **2.The free time – Museum:** Opportunities to see and get to know food processing. Almost like visiting a production. **3.The store - From me to you:** Instore farmers and/or production days, with farmers or food company staff would introduce their products and how they are made. Even answer some questions about the process. **4.The technology – QR:** QR code sticker on products where you can scan and get information about the nutrition or more. Most companies may find it easy to set up documents about their products and forward them rather than

video. **5.The innovation – Side products:** Create opportunities for young people to participate and create their own opportunities, based on information about unused side product raw materials or materials from domestic production. Could also be like a competition or just a game challenge.

Students in general showed positive attitudes towards all 5 ideas presented. They thought that the “from me to you” and the “side product innovation” ideas appealed most to their age group but the workshop idea and museum idea more to even younger generation.

Pitch 4: Less food waste with increased online shopping and consumer-friendly packaging. By selling groceries online, people can organize themselves better, buy less unnecessary items and have fewer shopping trips. By planning, people can reduce waste of everything considerably and people are also likely to buy healthier food when they shop online.

Students seemed to agree with the pitcher.

Pitch 5: Increased certified label marking to make online shopping easier. Online stores revealing more than price, like country of origin, if it is vegan, if it is organic, gluten-free or environmentally friendly. With this classification, it should be possible to check a box, e.g. gluten free to see the selection of all gluten-free products.

Students found this a very good idea but would rather benefit those who are already concerned about their consumption behaviour.

The most appreciated pitch was the food science web page. An information web page, a database where chefs, butchers, bakers, scientists, and others, answer questions from consumers about anything and everything related to food or food processing. Weekly podcast, recipes, cooking videos, production documentaries and blogs about food.

In Iceland it is not possible to find a comparable supply of food podcasts as in many other countries and people seem to be in demand for such.

Because of the workshop time frame, the question of DOs and DON'Ts for the industry were requested to be answered via email after the workshop. Four out of seven student participants replied with the following answers.

DO's and DON'T's

Product and production information

- ✓ **DO Increase clear and simple labels** in stores and on packaging about certain characteristics of the product (e.g., organic, Icelandic, vegan, free of allergens and footprints or other environmental impact labels) to make it easier for people to shop according to their values. **Increase product labelling** on which parts of the packaging are classified as what and design the packaging so that it is as simple as possible to distinguish different materials and sort them correctly.
- ✓ **DO Provide information on how and why** they conduct their production as they do easy for the public to understand (e.g., if they prefer to use plastic packaging to reduce food waste rather than dropping the plastic to reduce packaging, explain both sides in a simple way). Explain their decision, for example on their website, even under a special tab on the company's environmental policy, where everyone can easily find that information and understand the reasons for it).

- ✓ **DON'T Be too technical in presentation.** Young people should be able to easily understand the message.

Educational communication

- ✓ **DO Increase education and easy-to-understand information on how food production works** to increase the public's understanding of the process and what lies behind the product in the store.
- ✓ **DO Contribute to creating fun educational material for all ages**, e.g., with museums and videos. Educate us about the production and use of raw materials.
- ✓ **DO Have the conversation with the young people** (like these workshops) "nothing about us without us"

Trust and communication

- ✓ **DO Increase transparency in production with the help of independent parties** and thus increase trust, cf. the idea of a food science website to discuss the food industry in Iceland. This could be **Interest groups**, cf. the food science web idea
- ✓ **DO Introduce people to misconceptions** about the food industry and inform their consumers.
- ✓ **DO Keep an open discussion with consumers** and be ready to answer their questions.
- ✓ **DO Approach young people by many different methods or directions**, but preferably under one name (association/brand/company)
- ✓ **DON'T Hide information from consumers** (rather to provide better information to avoid unnecessary fears).
- ✓ **DON'T Try too hard to be "young"**, e.g. by advertise themselves on TikTok with dancing staff for example.

Societal responsibility

- ✓ **DO Reduce your environmental impact** as much as possible and give consumers the most environmentally friendly options (regarding packaging, waste of raw materials, use of animal products in products, greenhouse gases, energy consumption, imports, carbon footprint, etc.)
- ✓ **DO Show how Iceland gives them a unique position**, E.g.: as the geothermal use in saltworks for example.
- ✓ **DO Make an effort to re-establish people's connection with food** - state-funded e.g.
- ✓ **DON'T Be neutral towards societal challenges**, but take a stand if the opportunity arises
- ✓ **DON'T Bear sole responsibility for educating future generations** about food, although its help is certainly useful.
- ✓ **DON'T Do everything as "usual"** just because it has always been done that way, without thinking.

To fulfil the NGCs needs for knowledge, the national health authorities, or the government would need to step in and cooperate with the industry to provide satisfactory, scientifically sound information.

3.4 Evaluation of workshops

Effectiveness of the whole process in determining new strategies for communication and as a means of solving key challenges in the future:

All workshop participants had positive attitudes towards this discussion group method and believed it could be used as a mean of solving key challenges in the future.

“Healthy and solid discussions. Not like a conflict discussion but an exchange of views which is particularly important.” (Industry, female).

“This foundation of having a conversation is valuable and matters the most. We really appreciate criticism and are always ready to listen, although we cannot always respond immediately.” (Industry, female).

“It is great to get the opportunity to speak directly to companies and tell them what we think is most important.” (Male, student).

“After this meeting I feel very hopeful for the future.” (Female, student)

“What stands out for me is to hear directly from people who are currently working in the food industry, both in marketing and production. To hear how much thinking is behind each product and so many details in the production and the whole value chain. Just that companies are doing all of this is something we never think about so this was just a very delightful for me”. (Female, student)

The food industry representatives expressed that this experience of participating in this series of the WeValueFood workshops was knowledgeable, gave great ideas, good speculations and was fun with constructive discussions.

For the students they were thankful for the opportunity to have the discussion, were more hopeful towards the future after hearing from the industry, surprised to hear how complicated the food value chain really is and in general felt the workshop was just overall delightful.

4. Conclusions and recommendations

All workshop participants, both industry and students had positive attitudes towards the workshop discussions and believed it could be used as a mean of solving key challenges in the future.

NGCs place emphasis on environmental issues, and solid information from food industry. The main communication channels are mainly via social media, but the NGCs also emphasized other channels, such as information within food stores, and via food industries homepages. Transparency and honesty in communication is important to them, but it was preferred that food industry information is verified by a responsible third party, such as scientists and health authorities.

Industry participants did not find the views of the students surprising, but underlining what they had heard, for example regarding food waste. Although NGCs are interested in visiting food industry, it can be difficult due to safety control issues, but videos could help. Making informative, high quality videos,

is however, very expensive and time demanding. There was an agreement that collaboration was needed, and a common platform with independent academics would help. Although it should not be the responsibility of the food company/industry to educate NGCs, it is the companies/industries responsibility to provide information about their own products. NGCs are an environmentally conscious generation that demands or expects high quality information, fast. The fast response requirement from NGCs is difficult to meet, but it is very important to communicate with this generation of consumers, not the least as misinformation is easily distributed. Further, a need for a databank and formulas to calculate carbon footprint for each product would be desirable, to save time and increase trust.

From the **students-industry** workshop, it was clear that environmental issues are of great importance to the next generation of consumers along with information of the carbon footprint and the industry is generally aware of consumer's needs, as well as the means of communication. The industry often faces barriers to meet specific NGC needs, and those barriers are mainly related to cost, time and regulations. If the industry is doing something positive today, it can advertise itself, not the least via the next generation that shares everything on social media.

There is a high need for more educational material on video format like documentaries, how it's made short videos and plain edutainment (education/entertainment). To fulfil the NGCs needs for knowledge, the national health authorities, or the government would need to step in and cooperate with the industry to provide satisfactory, scientifically valid and trustworthy information available for everyone. Therefore, the industry calls for cooperation to educate the next generation on food related issues. General information from health authorities and schools, as well as possible interest groups, but all specialized information from the companies must come from themselves.

One of the pitches from the industry really summarised the overall need for communication, and could provide a very useful platform, both for food industry, but not the least, **NGC to meet their needs for specific food knowledge that could also improve their food involvement and engagement**. The food science platform/website, supervised by independent parties, such as universities, to provide fact based, scientifically correct information, without any conflicts of interest.

The DO's and DON'T's provided from the students to the industry representatives, summarise very well recommendations for the food industry today:

- ✓ Increase clear and simple labels
- ✓ Provide information on how and why they conduct their production as they do easy for the public to understand
- ✓ Increase education and easy-to-understand information on how food production works
- ✓ Contribute to creating fun educational material for all ages
- ✓ Approach young people by many different methods or directions
- ✓ Reduce your environmental impact

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References

Sveinsdóttir K, Jónsdóttir EM, Þorkelsson G, Guðlaugsdóttir BL, Ólafsdóttir AS, Jaworska, D, Affeltowicz D, Maison D, Chilewska M, Heikkilä M, Kuusjärvi S, Arnoult M, Mauchline A (2020). Report on industry communication to consumers, DEL01, EIT FOOD.